

EVALUATION OF INDICATORS OF INFLAMMATION IN THE PREOPERATIVE PERIOD OF SEPTOPLASTY

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ABSTRACT

Assessment of inflammatory markers in the preoperative period is important for predicting the functional results of septoplasty.

The analysis showed that the level of C-reactive protein (CRP) in the preoperative period generally did not meet the criteria for an acute inflammatory process, but when comparing between subgroups, a certain pattern was revealed. The data obtained suggest that even a moderate increase in the level of CRP may reflect latent inflammatory activity, which can affect the functional outcome of surgical treatment. This highlights the importance of preoperative assessment of inflammatory indicators for patient stratification and optimization of treatment tactics.

Introduction.

Violation of nasal breathing is one of the most common reasons for patients to go to an otorhinolaryngologist, while the leading role among anatomical factors is played by the curvature of the nasal septum, which requires surgical correction[1].

However, despite the technical sophistication of the intervention, in some cases the postoperative functional results remain unsatisfactory, which indicates the presence of additional pathogenetic factors affecting the outcome of treatment [2,3,4].

The aim of the study is to assess the role of allergic inflammation of the nasal mucosa before septoplasty.

Materials and methods. The study was conducted with the participation of 160 patients with nasal septal deformity and nasal breathing disorders who underwent examination and surgical treatment in the period from 2022 to 2025. Depending on the chronology of work stages, patients were divided into two groups:

- the control group consisted of 78 (48.8%) patients who underwent standard methods of diagnosis and surgical treatment during 2022-2023 with parallel determination of allergological and immunological parameters without changing the standard management tactics;

- the main group consisted of 82 (51.2%) patients who, in the period from 2024-2025, used the methods developed by us for predicting and preventing adverse functional outcomes according to the treatment and diagnostic algorithm developed by us.

Results. Analysis of the studied parameters before surgery revealed that before surgery, the level of CRP concentration did not look like a marker of an acute inflammatory outbreak. But at the same time, with the variance of this indicator among subgroups of patients, we identified a regular character. So, in the subgroup of patients with a "good" functional result of surgery, the CRP level exceeded the reference values by 1.47 times, while with a "satisfactory" outcome, it was already higher and reached a difference of 2.16 times.

Conclusion. The data obtained suggest that even a moderate increase in the level of CRP may reflect latent inflammatory activity, which can affect the functional outcome of surgical treatment. This highlights the importance of preoperative assessment of inflammatory indicators for patient stratification and optimization of treatment tactics..

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